

20231027 minimal surface contact chloroplast and mitochondria *T. oceanica* and *T. pseudonana* in Fe limitation

Jhoanell Angulo

2023-10-27

```
## [1] "D:/Users/Jhoanell/Documents/~Jhoanell 2025/Labo/Thalassiosira_project/~Thesis work/paper chloro"
```

Since there is less mitochondria in *To* than in *Tp*, it want to represent percentage of contact and normalize to area of chloroplast First I calculate surface contact by chloroplast

t_test for means

```
## # A tibble: 4 x 12
##   media organelle .y. group1 group2 n1 n2 statistic df p
##   <fct> <fct> <chr> <chr> <chr> <int> <int> <dbl> <dbl> <dbl>
## 1 100_Fe chloroplast cont_per To Tp 10 11 -4.90 12.8 3.08e-4
## 2 100_Fe mitochondria cont_per To Tp 10 11 -2.32 18.3 3.18e-2
## 3 5_Fe chloroplast cont_per To Tp 9 11 -5.59 11.3 1.47e-4
## 4 5_Fe mitochondria cont_per To Tp 9 11 -5.79 14.4 4.16e-5
## # i 2 more variables: p.adj <dbl>, p.signif <chr>
```


media 100_Fe 5_Fe genotype To

dia 100_Fe genotype ledia 5_Fe genotype

Increasing of surface contact by distance, only with respect to mitochondria and ratio of increase

t_test for means

```
## # A tibble: 8 x 13
##   genotype media  organelle  .y.  group1 group2  n1  n2  statistic  df
##   <fct>    <fct> <fct>    <chr> <chr> <chr> <int> <int>    <dbl> <dbl>
## 1 To      100_Fe chloroplast cont_p~ 30    50     10   10    -1.36   15.8
## 2 To      5_Fe   chloroplast cont_p~ 30    50     9    9     -1.22   12.8
## 3 To      100_Fe mitochondria cont_p~ 30    50     10   10    -0.967  16.5
## 4 To      5_Fe   mitochondria cont_p~ 30    50     9    9     -1.35   12.9
## 5 Tp      100_Fe chloroplast cont_p~ 30    50     11   11    -2.17   19.0
## 6 Tp      5_Fe   chloroplast cont_p~ 30    50     11   11    -2.16   18.3
## 7 Tp      100_Fe mitochondria cont_p~ 30    50     11   11    -2.17   18.9
## 8 Tp      5_Fe   mitochondria cont_p~ 30    50     11   11    -2.60   18.4
## # i 3 more variables: p <dbl>, p.adj <dbl>, p.signif <chr>
```


t_test for means

```
## # A tibble: 8 x 13
##   genotype organelle dist  .y.  group1 group2  n1  n2  statistic  df  p
##   <fct>      <fct>    <fct> <chr> <chr> <chr> <int> <int>    <dbl> <dbl> <dbl>
## 1 To        chloropl~ 30  cont~ 100_Fe 5_Fe    10   9     0.539  13.2 0.599
## 2 To        mitochon~ 30  cont~ 100_Fe 5_Fe    10   9     1.43   10.5 0.182
## 3 To        chloropl~ 50  cont~ 100_Fe 5_Fe    10   9     1.04   14.5 0.314
## 4 To        mitochon~ 50  cont~ 100_Fe 5_Fe    10   9     1.61   11.4 0.135
## 5 Tp        chloropl~ 30  cont~ 100_Fe 5_Fe    11  11     0.943  18.5 0.358
## 6 Tp        mitochon~ 30  cont~ 100_Fe 5_Fe    11  11     0.683  17.7 0.504
## 7 Tp        chloropl~ 50  cont~ 100_Fe 5_Fe    11  11     1.20   19.1 0.245
## 8 Tp        mitochon~ 50  cont~ 100_Fe 5_Fe    11  11     0.863  18.2 0.399
## # i 2 more variables: p.adj <dbl>, p.signif <chr>
```


media 5_Fe genotype I